

INTERACTIVE TEACHING AND LEARNING METHODS

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Аннотация: *Данной статье рассматриваются инновационные методики обучения русского языка и литературы, Современное образование должно быть ориентировано на подготовку учащихся к успешной методике обучения играют ключевую роль в достижении этой цели, так как они способствуют активному развитию творческих способностей и интеллектуальной активности учеников. социализации и адаптации на рынке труда в быстро меняющемся обществе.*

Annotation: *This article examines innovative methods for teaching Russian language and literature. Modern education should be focused on preparing students for success. These methods play a key role in achieving this goal, as they promote the active development of students' creative abilities and intellectual activity. They also contribute to their socialization and adaptation to the labor market in a rapidly changing society.*

Ключевые слова: *инновация, методика, обучения, проблема, аналитическое мышления, мотивационное методика, креативное мышление, поиск, решений.*

Key words: *innovation, methodology, learning, problem, analytical thinking, motivational technique, creative thinking, search, solutions.*

Modern educators increasingly recognize that problem-based learning leads to a deeper understanding of the material and active student engagement in the learning process. Therefore, the development and application of innovative teaching methods is becoming an important component of modern teaching practice.

Indeed, strategies that directly influence the learning process and strategies that create the conditions for learning and overcoming psychological difficulties can be considered as two main groups. 1. Cognitive strategies: These strategies help students comprehend and structure the material they are studying. These include methods of analysis, comparison, generalization, and others. Cognitive strategies help students effectively process information and assimilate it.

2. Memorization strategies: These are aimed at retaining information in memory. These strategies may include the use of mnemonic devices, repetition, organizing information into diagrams, and others. Memorization strategies help students consolidate the material they have learned and recall it more easily in the future.

3. Compensatory Strategies: These strategies help learners overcome difficulties that arise during learning or communicating in a foreign language. They include techniques such as searching for additional information, using context to understand unfamiliar words, using idioms to express their thoughts, etc.

The second group of strategies is related to creating favorable learning conditions and overcoming psychological difficulties:

1. Strategies for Creating Conditions for Learning: These strategies include organizing the learning space, using various teaching methods, and support from teachers and the community. Creating a suitable learning environment promotes effective learning.

2. Strategies for Overcoming Psychological Difficulties: These are aimed at supporting students in overcoming stress, anxiety, uncertainty, and other psychological problems that may arise during the learning process. These strategies may include motivational techniques, relaxation methods, counseling, and support from teachers and psychologists. Both groups of strategies are important for successful learning and contribute to the effective acquisition of educational material and the development of study skills in students. The development of modern educational technologies has brought significant changes to the educational process and teaching methods, particularly in the field of foreign language learning. The introduction of audio and video recordings, computer programs, and distance learning has significantly enriched the learning environment and provided students with new opportunities for effective learning.

One of the main advantages of using information technology in education is the ability to create interactive and adaptive learning materials that can be tailored to the individual needs of each student. This allows each student to develop at their own pace and level, which facilitates more effective knowledge acquisition.

Innovative teaching methods focused on active student participation also play an important role in modern pedagogy. Engaging students in activities, collaborative work, and the exchange of opinions not only promotes a deeper understanding of the material but also develops communication and social skills. Thus, innovative approaches to teaching and the use of modern educational technologies help make the learning process more interactive, accessible, and effective for all students, ultimately contributing to their successful learning and development.

1. Working proactively, anticipating development: Innovative learning is focused on anticipating the future needs and demands of society and the labor market. This helps prepare students for the challenges they may face in the future and equips them with the necessary skills and knowledge to adapt successfully.

2. Openness to the Future: Innovative learning encourages students to be flexible, adaptive, and open to new ideas and opportunities. It stimulates creative thinking and the search for innovative solutions.
3. Focus on the individual and their development: Innovative learning takes into account the individual needs, interests, and abilities of each student. It aims not only to impart knowledge but also to develop personal development, critical thinking, and communication and social skills.
4. Mandatory Elements of Creativity: Innovative learning emphasizes stimulating students' creative thinking and activity. It encourages experimentation, exploration, and independent creativity.
5. Partnership-based relationships: Innovative learning builds relationships between teacher and student based on partnership, collaboration, and mutual support. It creates an atmosphere of trust and respect that promotes more effective learning and personal development.

Innovations in education are reflected in all aspects of the educational process and are aimed at improving its quality, adapting it to changing conditions and societal needs, and ensuring the personal development of each student.

The use of innovative teaching methods in teaching Russian language and literature not only helps develop students' creative abilities but also makes the learning process more interesting and productive. Let's take a closer look at some of them:

1. Clusters: This method helps organize and structure information in the form of association charts or diagrams. Students can use clusters to analyze texts, take notes, and organize their thoughts and ideas.
2. Inserts: This technique involves including additional information or comments while studying independently. It helps students better understand what they've read and expand their knowledge.
3. Table Completion: This method promotes the organization and comparison of information. Students can use tables to organize data, compare texts, and analyze characters and themes.
4. Two-Part Journal: This technique allows students to express their thoughts, reflections, and impressions in journal form, which promotes writing development and self-expression.
5. Stop-Reading: This method helps students gain a deeper understanding of the text, draw conclusions, and analyze plot lines and characters.
6. Collaborative Research: This technique encourages collective activity and the exchange of opinions, which contributes to the development of communication skills and creative thinking.

7. Cross-Discussion: This method allows students to express their arguments, analyze others' points of view, and develop argumentation and dialogue skills.

8. Using project-based learning in teaching Russian language and literature is truly an effective method for developing a variety of students' skills and abilities. Let's consider the main advantages of this approach:

1. Increased interest and motivation: Project-based activities stimulate students' interest because they have the opportunity to choose topics that interest them most and independently determine the direction of their research.

2. Developing creativity: Projects allow students to express their individuality by proposing original ideas and solutions, which fosters creativity.

3. Developing independent work and research skills: Participation in projects requires students to demonstrate independence, organizational skills, and the ability to work with large amounts of information, which develops their research skills.

4. Developing communication and collaboration skills: Group project work teaches students effective interaction, collaborative problem-solving, and develops communication and collaboration skills.

5. Creating an atmosphere of mutual respect and trust: Student participation in projects fosters an atmosphere of mutual respect and trust between them and the teacher, which positively impacts the overall classroom climate.

6. Encouraging teamwork and individual development: Projects allow students to discover and demonstrate their individual abilities and strengths while working in a team, which fosters teamwork and mutual support. Using project-based learning in Russian language and literature is an effective tool for promoting students' well-rounded development and creating a supportive learning environment.

The use of various non-traditional elements in the lesson, such as vocabulary dictation, riddle composition, annotated writing, and others, truly makes the lesson more interesting and engages students. It is important for students to find learning engaging and enjoyable, and this requires using a variety of methods and forms of work in the lesson. Such elements not only make the lesson more engaging but also develop students' creative thinking and foster a positive attitude toward the subject being studied.

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